

Praxis for Teaching University-level Critical Thinking Courses: Issues and Actions

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Abstract: *Critical thinking is a multilayered cognitive and affective process that involves analyzing information, making informed judgments, and examining previously formed beliefs to enrich decision-making. Its development is vital in higher education, as it provides the necessary tools for students to face the complexities of the world in which they must navigate. However, implementing critical thinking in education is complex, as historically demonstrated by the challenges depicted in Plato's Allegory of the Cave. This paper presents findings from a study conducted by the author, tasked with teaching a newly introduced critical thinking skills course in a Japanese university's English department. The study emerged due to unclear course guidelines and limited faculty support because the course was uncharted. Consequently, the author was faced with the undertaking of designing an effective syllabus, which required an extensive amount of praxis-oriented research and preparation. The paper delineates practical application of theoretical knowledge and pedagogical methods that stem from the author's firsthand encounters in implementing a critical thinking course. Details of critical thinking activities used in the course, and the pedagogies to support them are presented. The research features student feedback showing outcomes of the course. The study makes the claim that it is not only necessary to know the subject matter of what to teach, but it is equally important to know and select appropriate pedagogies of how to teach it. Implications are informative for faculty development, providing guidance to teachers who are presented with the challenges of teaching critical thinking skills within the curriculum.*

Keywords: critical thinking, pedagogy, teacher development, scaffolding

Introduction

Critical thinking encompasses cognitive and affective dimensions. It involves a deliberate process of making informed judgements by analyzing information to make better decisions, as well as challenging previously held beliefs that may cloud reasoning. Critical thinking empowers students and should not be neglected in higher education. Therefore, the development of critical thinking skills is essential in university curricula. However, critical thinking is not a natural learning outcome of

coursework. The praxis for teaching critical thinking involving knowledge and practical applications have been historically intricate and difficult to implement, mirroring the difficulties of disseminating knowledge depicted by the ancient philosopher Plato in his Allegory of the Cave more than 2,500 years ago. Thus, teaching a critical thinking course can be a daunting task.

This paper is based on a study conducted by the author, who was tasked with teaching a newly introduced critical thinking skills course in a department of English in a Japanese university. The study was initiated because the course guidelines were ambiguous without clear definition. Moreover, due to the novelty of the course, there was limited assistance offered for faculty development. Consequently, praxis-centered research seeking practical applications of theoretical knowledge concerned with critical thinking was necessary to develop the course. Issues that the author encountered during the planning and teaching of the course are presented in this paper, which include the importance of defining critical thinking; determining what skills and characteristics of the concept should be focused on; and selecting appropriate pedagogies to implement it.

The study, primarily centered on pedagogy, highlights the activities featured in a critical thinking skills development course and incorporates student feedback. A focused open-ended question was presented to the students to gather insights into how they understood the concept of critical thinking after taking the course. The study's implications are relevant to faculty development, as they provide guidance for teachers involved in professional improvement when tasked with teaching a critical thinking skills course within the curriculum.

Literature Review

Understanding critical thinking and methods for teaching it

While many teachers emphasize the importance of teaching critical thinking, a substantial number struggle to define it or effectively teach it. A study of 120 teachers across 57 Californian colleges found that 89% considered critical thinking a key course objective, yet only 19% could provide a clear definition, and a mere 9% effectively taught critical thinking development (Paul, Elder & Bartell, 1997). In a more focused investigation at a private liberal arts college, Halx and Reybold (2005) discovered that instructors were uncertain about which critical thinking skills to teach and lacked proper training for it. Despite being part of the same institution, they did not exchange information regarding their respective courses. The paucity of teacher development training was seen in another study carried out with EFL teachers in five universities in Colombia (Marin & de la Pava, 2017). They believed that the absence of well-defined institutional guidelines for promoting critical thinking content and activities was an obstacle. As a result, they stated that inadequate training was the primary factor that prevented them from effectively teaching critical thinking in their courses. The significance of the studies shows that the absence of faculty training designed to prepare teachers for their courses had practical consequences. They formulated their own approaches due to a lack of shared conceptual knowledge and pedagogical methods. In turn, the teachers were left to depend on personal intuition for instruction, which is prone to error.

The studies cited above, covering three decades, continuously underscore the vital role of professional pedagogical knowledge for incorporating critical thinking into the curriculum. Paul (2005) emphasized the necessity for teachers to possess a clear grasp of critical thinking and the pedagogical expertise required to effectively teach it. In the former case, because of the wide range of characterizations it is difficult to adopt a baseline working definition of critical thinking (Murawski,

2014), but as a first step to avoid confusion as shown in the studies above, a discussion among faculty may lead to a clarification of the basic skills associated with it. In the latter, teachers must possess teacher knowledge of suitable pedagogical methods, as traditional lecture-based instruction can contradict the principles of teaching critical thinking, which necessitates constructivist, interactive, student-centered, and collaborative approaches (Lai, 2011). Shulman's (1986) seminal work delineated teacher knowledge into two domains: content knowledge, pertaining to what to teach, and pedagogical knowledge, regarding how to teach it. He integrated these two domains, which will be addressed below, into the concept of pedagogical content knowledge (PCK).

Understanding the content knowledge domain of critical thinking

For all teachers, content knowledge of the subject they are teaching is essential. When setting out to teach a course centered on critical thinking, the immediate challenge is to form an understanding of a concept that has evolved over time, layered with definitions from various disciplines of philosophy, psychology, and education (Lai, 2011). Historically, the roots of critical thinking came to light centuries ago in ancient Greece, and it emerged as a core aim in education in the work of the educational philosopher John Dewey. In his book *How We Think* (1910), he argued for a coherent, discovery-oriented, student-centered approach toward the development of critical thinking skills in schools. He described critical thinking, which he mostly referred to as "reflective thinking" to be a learning process that involved:

[a]ctive, persistent, and careful consideration of a belief or supposed form of knowledge in the light of the grounds which support it and the further conclusions to which it tends (p. 6).

Dewey considered critical thinking from a cognitive and psychological standpoint that involved the interplay of certain characteristics and skills showing determination, discernment, and skepticism until proven judgements about claims emerge while examining one's beliefs. He opted for the term "warranted assertibility" (see Boyles, 2006, p.8) to avoid the risks of regarding knowledge as unquestionable facts detached from inquiry. His choice of words demonstrated that knowledge claims should be open-ended and subject to inquiry. Dewey maintained that facts are not infallible, and therefore, students should be actively engaged in a continuous, disciplined critical thinking process in their quest for understanding. A few decades later, research on critical thinking skill development was reestablished in consideration of Dewey's thoughts. For example, Bloom's (1956) taxonomy of higher order skills later revised by Anderson et al (2001) provided a useful heuristic. These models depicted applicable critical thinking skills at the higher end of a pyramid involving synthesizing and evaluating abilities leading to creating and knowledge building as an educational objective.

The 1980s featured a significant surge of research on critical thinking as scholars recognized the dynamic and systematic nature of the concept and its associated abilities. An academic organization that has been instrumental in supporting the field of critical thinking, led by researchers who are committed to promoting critical thinking in a range of disciplines, has offered a standard baseline definition for the organization:

Critical thinking is the intellectually disciplined process of actively and skillfully conceptualizing, applying, analyzing, synthesizing, and/or evaluating information gathered from, or

generated by, observation, experience, reflection, reasoning, or communication, as a guide to belief and action (Scriven & Paul, 1987, p. 1).

Facione extended the definition to not only focus on the individual's cognitive processes of critical thinking, but also the dialogic aspect of opening one's mind to the social realities of others:

The ability of a person to present well-reasoned arguments, and to evaluate correctly the arguments others present (1986, p. 222).

Ennis (1987) further contributed to a holistic shaping of the concept by offering a psychological and moral dimension to critical thinking by invoking a list of core dispositional skills a critical thinker should have. Ennis provided a list of criteria that included having skepticism but being willing to entertain new ideas until substantiated and to care about respecting the views of others and being open to belief change. Thus, Ennis argued for a balanced approach that blended skepticism with openness.

Understanding the pedagogical knowledge domain to teach critical thinking

Shulman's PCK model (1986) emphasized the crucial role of pedagogical knowledge in teaching to point out that teachers need to be aware of suitable teaching methods for course implementation. For university professors setting out to teach a critical thinking course, this requires not only possessing subject knowledge of critical thinking, but also knowing how to effectively teach it by selecting appropriate pedagogies. However, the pedagogical side of the equation can be a particular challenge to university instructors, who rely on traditional forms of instruction that are representative of monologic, transmission models of pedagogy driven by lectures, which regulate students to passive roles (e.g., Kumaravadivelu, 2012; Nygaard, Courtney & Holtham, 2014; van der Vleuten & Driessen, 2014). In short, these approaches contradict the principles of teaching critical thinking that prioritize active learning as advocated by Dewey. This entails a praxis-oriented pedagogical approach involving students as active participants in the knowledge-building process through hands-on experiences and reflective thinking. To effectively teach critical thinking, it becomes more appropriate to select approaches (including complementary methods, and techniques) that are aligned with social constructivist learning theories.

In this study, the use of a critical pedagogy approach, supported by inquiry-based and inductive learning methods, and guided instruction through scaffolding were identified as effective constructivist principles for teaching critical thinking. For example, critical pedagogy (as proposed by Freire, 1970; Giroux, 1988) aims at learner empowerment by challenging existing knowledge frameworks in education; inquiry-based learning (as described by Dewey 1938; Bruner, 1960; Vygotsky, 1978) promotes questioning, exploration, and active learning; inductive learning (as advocated by Darling-Hammond et. al, 2008) involves helping students make new meanings based on observations and evidence rather than starting with a theory. These approaches promote critical thinking, reflection, and action. Scaffolding can support these approaches. The concept of scaffolding, as originally put forward by Wood, Bruner, and Ross (1976), and termed assisted performance by Tharp and Gallimore (1988) provides support and guidance to learners as they work on specific tasks. This teaching or mentoring assistance is offered at various stages of the learning process, with the optimum aim of helping learners achieve their learning goals within their "zone of proximal development" (Vygotsky, 1978, p. 86): differentiating between what they can do on their own and what

they can do with assistance from others. Basically, scaffolding is a teaching technique in which teachers provide the necessary and timely assistance to learners, enabling them to develop the required skills and understanding to reach their optimal learning potential, at a stage termed by Tharp and Gallimore (1988) as “automatization” (p. 35), in which they no longer need assistance.

The Study

In this section, an introductory critical thinking course syllabus that was designed by the author is shown. It consisted of 18 English major students who were in their first year. The syllabus was organized around the International Baccalaureate (IB) curriculum, which is deeply rooted in critical thinking development (Takegami, 2023). This is reflected in the curriculum’s epistemological focus on exploring theories of knowing (TOK) to determine appropriate theoretical models, types of evidence, and how theories relate to real-life situations through different ways of knowing (WOK) such as emotion, reason, faith, language, perception, intuition, memory, and imagination. Additionally, the curriculum includes the analytical approaches suitable for subject areas of knowing (AOK) such as mathematics, the arts, history, indigenous knowledge, natural science through observation, and the scientific method, as noted by Sprague (2020). Classes were conducted over a five-week period, meeting once a week for 90 minutes.

The lessons presented below go beyond generalized taxonomies or categorical descriptions of kinds of critical thinking activities. Instead, actual descriptions of activities and appropriate pedagogies used in the classes are detailed in a sequential manner, starting from week one and progressing to week five. They are given to emphasize the practical applications of PCK.

Table 1. *Description of activities and corresponding pedagogies*

1st class Activities	Pedagogical Approach:
Activity 1: An inductive brainstorming approach is used to tap into students’ existing knowledge. They were prompted to jot down words or phrases that popped into their heads when they heard “critical thinking”. Responses were shared and discussed as a whole class, promoting engagement and activating prior knowledge.	Inductive learning techniques to encourage learners to draw from their prior understanding of the concept were employed.
Activity 2: Introduced Plato’s Allegory of the Cave and explored critical thinking for discussion questions. The allegory illustrates challenges of critical thinking in education, as prisoners in the story solely rely on their knowledge and preconceived beliefs drawn from cave shadows. When one prisoner, who is allowed to go out of the cave, becomes enlightened by seeing reality beyond the shadows, tries to share the truth, others resist, highlighting the difficulty within the educational process of developing critical thinkers.	A critical pedagogy approach aimed at challenging dominant narratives and belief systems was adopted. Through this story, students learned the value of education for personal development and societal change. In this inductive activity, students discussed the story and were given opportunities to conclude that humans can make flawed judgments, emphasizing the importance of critical thinking education in guiding them out of their metaphorical caves.

<p>2nd class Activities</p> <p>Activity 3: In this activity, students were provided with cognitive structuring scaffolds to aid their development of critical thinking skills. These scaffolds were based on the IB curriculum TOK (Theory of Knowledge) and the frameworks of WOK (Ways of Knowing) and AOK (Areas of Knowledge). A reading was given to the students with knowledge claims. Then, a worksheet was provided to decode the information to epistemologically determine How do we know what we know? The handout offered a framework with places to identify WOK and AOK. In pairs, students worked together to complete the decoding worksheet.</p>	<p>Pedagogical Approach:</p> <p>A scaffolded teaching method was used, drawing from Tharp and Gallimore's work (1988) depicting teacher strategies to assist students' performance, including instruction, cognitive structuring, and modeling, to introduce TOK, WOK, and AOK. These concepts were given to assist students in analyzing the content of knowledge claims made in the reading. The activity was collaborative and socially interactive since students worked in pairs to do critical analysis as a first step to help foster critical thinking.</p>
<p>Activity 4: Students were tasked with exploring TOK in the context of teeth whitening knowledge claims, with natural science as the selected AOK. They analyzed two pre-selected toothpaste commercials and were assigned homework to formulate questions using WOK to further develop their critical thinking skills.</p>	<p>This activity followed a critical pedagogy and inquiry-based learning approach.</p>
<p>3rd Class</p> <p>Activity 5: In a continuation of activity 4, students were further guided in the critical thinking task. Groups of three students were assigned to analyze two commercials and complete a decoding handout, facilitating critical dialogue. Questions emerged, such as the significance of white teeth and the actual healthiness of whitened teeth. Through dialogical interactions, ethical and scientific issues were critically addressed, revealing that naturally healthy teeth can have a slightly off-white color.</p>	<p>Pedagogical Approach:</p> <p>This activity was framed by a critical pedagogy approach, challenging the prevailing narrative about the desirability of teeth whitening. Inquiry-based learning allowed students to engage in hands-on discovery.</p>
<p>4th Class</p> <p>Activity 6: The focus shifted to critically examining AOK relative to natural science and indigenous knowledge systems. Students collaborated on a project to examine whether folk medicinal remedies could be supported with natural science data. Although the topic was pre-selected, the students chose their commercial examples, gathered data, provided interpretations, and formed conclusions, documenting the critical thinking process in computer slide presentations.</p>	<p>Pedagogical Approach:</p> <p>Like Activity 4, this activity relied on critical pedagogy and inquiry-based learning. It also incorporated collaborative and project-based learning methods. At this stage in their critical thinking skill development, and due to the introductory nature of the subject, scaffolded steps designed in the course were implemented to guide the students to reach the learning goal of the task.</p>
<p>5th Class</p> <p>Activity 7: Group presentations showed connections between folk remedies and natural sciences through critical analysis. The final writing assignment required students to 1) reflect on their group performance and 2) evaluate another group's presentation.</p>	<p>Pedagogical Approach:</p> <p>This activity embraced social constructivism, emphasizing collaboration through project-based learning. It also included an individual task for self-reflection and critical evaluation.</p> <p>In future activities, students are to receive less guidance, giving students opportunities to internalize their learning leading to the stage of "automatization."</p>

The seven activities over the course of five classes used pedagogies that were conducive to teaching critical thinking skills, which require tenets associated with active learning. Although the course applied those pedagogies, the key to bringing the pedagogies together was scaffolding.

Through scaffolding, the pedagogies were adapted, but guided with activities facilitated by the author. In future courses, as students become more knowledgeable of critical thinking, less guidance can be applied.

Part of this study bringing theory to practice was to outline the course design through describing activities and the underpinning pedagogies to implement them. In addition, an effort was made to learn what the students thought about critical thinking and the course.

Method

At the end of the course, an inquiry for the purpose of eliciting student feedback about the introductory critical thinking course was conducted with 18 students. The inquiry was qualitative in nature. A single exploratory question was given to the students to elicit a focused response about how they viewed critical thinking after taking the course. Part of the question was formed in response to a particular issue. The issue involved the Japanese translation of “critical”, which is *hihanteki*. In Japanese, it carries a negative connotation. Bullsmith (2020) wrote that replacing critical thinking with the term of logical thinking might be more positive because it “lacks the negative connotation of critical, so educators and policy makers who shrink from ‘hostile’ thinking in school curricula can agree on the need for logical thinking” (p.111). Therefore, of particular relevance to this study regarding teacher development, in addition to delineating the activities, pedagogies and course content, was the reported notion that the negative connotation has led some teachers in Japan to hesitate to teach it, as noted by Nomura (2023). In an interview with 12 school teachers, he found that most of them did not know that it had become part of the national curriculum guidelines even though Bullsmith found after going through the entire MEXT (Ministry of Education) website that critical thinking was alluded to approximately 1,200 times. Bullsmith also posited that teaching critical thinking skills as in debate activities requires a teacher to perform the role of “devil’s advocate” (2020, p.113), which may be seen as supporting a wrong answer, and makes them vulnerable to criticism from parents or being accused of having politically biased views.

In response to the above, because of past educational experiences, the 1st year students may or may not have formed views on critical thinking and the type of skills to apply them. Thus, the focused question set out to elicit a developmental understanding of course participants after finishing the course. The question was formed to gather qualitative data and designed to be open-ended as follows: *What does critical thinking mean to you?*

Data analysis

Because of the qualitative, open-ended nature of the question, a comparison analysis was conducted to locate similar patterns found in the responses. The 18 responses were coded and categorized into two areas by the author. To encapsulate these replies, six responses were labeled, Changing views from negative to positive about the term critical thinking and 12 responses were depicted as Awareness of gaining critical thinking skills.

Changing views from negative to positive about the term “critical thinking”

As for critical thinking, I had an image of criticizing something and hurting someone, such as giving someone negative opinions. But I have come to think that it is something that

allowed me to grow different perspectives by having curiosity and doubts about everything around me.

I used to think that “thinking critically about a topic” means thinking from the standpoint of denying your own ideas, but I have come to think it important to deepen our thoughts, that is, not trying to deny something but trying to think that the issue must be associated with other fields as well.

At first, I thought critical thinking meant being negative and we should avoid discussing the issues around us. But through the course, I have learned a new way of thinking and knowledge by adapting the ideas of AOK (areas of knowledge) and we can make relevance to other areas.

The image of the word “critical” was negative, but I think it is necessary for university education to be able to deepen our knowledge by grasping things broadly and flexibly.

Regarding critical thinking, I had a negative perspective about being ‘critical’, I have learned critical thinking skills are very practical tools to help our thinking process deepen with reasons.

I am not good at expressing my thoughts and I thought it was negative to have critical thinking, but now I think it means that we should have a multi-faceted way in looking at things.

Awareness of gaining critical thinking skills

I learned about taking an inquiry-based approach to studying an issue by asking certain questions, such as: What is the connection to other areas? How did we get this information? Why do we think in this way? These are what I deeply tried to do for inquiring and generating my opinion and making inferences.

The process of WOK has helped me cultivate critical thinking, and I have come to know that one issue must be associated with other issues as well, which I hadn’t thought of before.

The process of critical thinking has made it possible for me to think about the events that are happening around me in relation to myself rather than someone else’s affairs.

It’s fun to think from multiple perspectives, and I feel like I’ve become a little wiser in the process of having various ideas and discussing them.

I learned that many issues around us entail critical views. For example, what is seemingly not necessary turned out to be important and necessary.

By seeing and comparing the information, I have a wider view to perceive the issues, which make it easy for me to make an inference.

We have much information around us such as fake news and mind controlling ones. Through this critical thinking course, I think I’ve acquired the skills to see whether information is evidence-based and what is the purpose of it.

I have changed my thinking process and I feel that I can explain why I have an opinion. I think it is very important.

In order to generate the questions from real life situations with different data and information, I could make inferences that are persuasive.

I have come to be skeptical about the news and daily information. Now I would like to consider what this and that means more carefully with reasons.

I have come to think more logically and not ambiguously. From different data and information, I need to be more careful to believe it or not. Unconsciously, might our mind be controlled?

I feel I have come to have a much wider view of the issue; such as why? How? Now, I think I have better skills of seeing the issues more objectively

Results

All 18 students responded. The responses were labelled into two categories. A third of the students chose to emphasize the change in how they understood the term “critical thinking”. Two-thirds of the students’ responses were in recognition of how important it was for them to develop analytical and inquiry-based skills.

The responses reveal the transformative impact of the critical thinking course on students’ perceptions of what they think critical thinking is and the abilities they gained that will assist them in doing it. They have moved from negative or limited views of critical thinking to a more positive, practical, and comprehensive understanding of the concept. Students were able to consider multiple perspectives, transforming the negative connotation of “critical” into recognition of its necessity in higher education. As one student responded, “The image of the word “critical” was negative, but I think it is necessary for university education to be able to deepen our knowledge by grasping things broadly and flexibly.” Moreover, they acknowledged the real-world applicability of having critical thinking skills. For example, “I have come to be skeptical about the news and daily information. Now I would like to consider what this and that means more carefully with reasons.” The responses of the 18 students suggest they believed they had gained favorable learning experiences from the course. This feedback can be encouraging for teachers who aim at instruction that can empower students to think critically, communicate effectively, and approach complex issues with a broader and more open-minded perspective.

Implications

This paper underscores strategies of educational praxis the author used for teaching a critical thinking course in a university setting. The documentation of the class activities, pedagogies that underpinned them along with the data from the respondents produced in this study contribute to the field by providing examples that have potential for transferability (Glaser, 1998; Trochim, 2006). Thus, the findings, although they cannot be generalized, have potential to be transferable in cases to other similar academic settings to provide constructive insights for faculty development emphasizing appropriate PCK, definitions of critical thinking, and activities designed to implement

it. In turn, the research pointed out several important criteria to consider when setting out to teach a critical thinking course at the university level:

Defining Critical Thinking: The study stressed the need for a clear definition of critical thinking for teachers. Many instructors struggle to come up with a definition of the term although they agree on its importance (Paul, Elder & Bartel, 1997). Because it is a complex concept with various definitions, several leading scholars listed in this study formed a working definition for it. Therefore, even though there are multiple ways to define critical thinking, to avoid confusion, faculties should formulate a working definition of the concept as a first step.

Having Pedagogical Knowledge: It is important for teachers to be familiar with appropriate teaching methods aligned with principles of critical thinking. Teacher knowledge of active learning, inquiry-based methods and constructivist approaches is essential for creating engaging and interactive learning environments.

Using Scaffolding to Prepare for Constructivist Approaches: As suggested in this study, constructivist approaches, including critical pedagogy and inquiry-based learning using student-centered and collaborative strategies are effective to replace traditional lecture-based methods in teaching critical thinking. However, moving away from the latter approach requires attention or PCK to designing steps to help assist the performance of students who are unfamiliar with critical thinking as the results of the questionnaire show.

Applying an Interdisciplinary Approach: To further application and comprehension across domains, critical thinking courses should combine various epistemological approaches, drawing from theories of knowing (TOK), ways of knowing (WOK), and areas of knowledge (AOK) as demarcated in the International Baccalaureate (IB) curriculum.

Broadening Perspectives: Based on student feedback, critical thinking courses broaden students' perspectives, enriching open-minded and logical thinking. The inclusion of critical thinking courses fulfills an education goal of universities to further personal and academic development.

Meaningful Teaching Development: Insights that emerged from this study may have the potential for transferability informing other teachers in similar situations who are interested in enhancing their PCK, enabling them to teach critical thinking and develop effective courses. In doing so, it is important to know how the concept has evolved historically, be familiar with its various definitions embodying both cognitive and affective domains, and have knowledge of interdisciplinary approaches.

Conclusion

This research offers insights that emerged from the author's firsthand praxis experiences with the challenges and opportunities of teaching critical thinking in a university context. Actual activities used in the course were outlined. Appropriate pedagogies used to implement the activities were listed. Student responses reflected positive outcomes of the course. These results offer insights

into why the development of critical thinking skills play a crucial role in university education. In turn, PCK development in teaching critical thinking can ultimately benefit both teachers and students in fostering critical thinking skills. If courses designed to teach critical thinking skills do not use suitable pedagogies, then learning is minimized. The research outlined in this study may lead to future contributions toward professional pedagogical development in the area of teaching critical thinking skills to students to better prepare them to think critically and reflectively.

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